

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/jsams

Original research

Prenatal determinants of youth physical fitness: Maternal BMI before pregnancy, gestational length, physical activity, and gestational anemia. The UP&DOWN study

Carmen Padilla-Moledo ^{a,b,*}, Alejandro Pérez-Bey ^{a,b}, Sandra Sánchez-Parente ^{a,b}, Rocio Izquierdo-Gómez ^{a,b}, Oscar L. Veiga ^c, Jose Castro-Piñero ^{a,b}

^a GALENO Research Group, Department of Physical Education, Faculty of Education Sciences, University of Cadiz, Spain

^b Instituto de Investigación e Innovación Biomédica de Cádiz (INIBICA), Cádiz, Spain

^c Department of Physical Education, Sport and Human Movement, Faculty of Education, Autonomous University of Madrid, Ciudad Universitaria de Cantoblanco, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 18 June 2025

Received in revised form 6 November 2025

Accepted 20 January 2026

Available online xxxx

Keywords:

Pregnancy

Obesity

Pregnancy length

Anemia

Exercise

Offspring

ABSTRACT

Objectives: Our purpose is to investigate the relative weight of prenatal determinants on children's and adolescents' physical fitness outcomes at different ages.

Design: Cross-sectional study with retrospectively collected data.

Methods: We obtained data from 1188 children (571 girls) aged 6–11 years and 1020 adolescents (495 girls) aged 12–17 years. Maternal prenatal determinants were self-reported by mothers. The ALPHA fitness test battery for youth was used to assess offspring's physical fitness (motor fitness, cardiorespiratory fitness and muscular strength). Regression analyses were performed to examine the different physical fitness outcomes.

Results: **Higher maternal BMI before pregnancy** was positively associated with lower physical fitness levels in offspring, regardless of age and sex; offspring of mothers who were **physically active before to and during pregnancy** exhibited higher physical fitness levels, specifically in female adolescents (all $p < 0.05$). The **length of gestation** was positively associated with physical fitness in male adolescents and **absence of gestational anemia** was related to higher physical fitness levels in female children (all $p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Our results show the strongest prenatal determinants of physical fitness in children and adolescents and can contribute to the development of health promotion programs that could start even before children are born.

© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of Sports Medicine Australia. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Practical implications

- This study identifies key prenatal factors associated with children's and adolescents' physical fitness, highlighting the relevance of maternal health even before pregnancy.
- The strongest prenatal determinants of offspring physical fitness were maternal BMI before pregnancy, maternal physical activity before and during pregnancy, normal gestational length ($\geq 34 \leq 42$ weeks), and the absence of gestational anemia.
- Since these public health domain factors seem to be of great importance for a child's long-term development, future intervention studies are needed to confirm whether improving these maternal factors can causally influence offspring's physical fitness outcomes.

1. Introduction

Scientific literature evidences that many adult chronic diseases could have their origins in fetal life.¹ Consistently, maternal metabolic status can influence the intrauterine environment in which the offspring are developed and subsequently affecting offspring health, and a suboptimal intra-uterine environment could alter offspring metabolism and cell function. Moreover, this effect could be translated into adulthood, increasing susceptibility to non-communicable diseases later in life.¹

Physical fitness attributes have been used to assess functional health and mediate health-related quality of life in children.^{2,3} Motor fitness, cardiorespiratory fitness and muscular strength are major health markers in children and adolescents.^{4–6} Hence, a high level of physical fitness is associated with a healthier cardiovascular profile,⁷ healthy maternal BMI status,^{8,9} self-reported health,^{2,10} and cumulative incidence of mental disorders (i.e. anxiety and depression) in children and adolescents.¹¹ For instance, evidence suggests that some prenatal determinants such as hypertensive disorders in pregnancy,¹²

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: carmen.padilla@uca.es (C. Padilla-Moledo).

Social media: [@galenoresearch](https://x.com/galenoresearch) (C. Padilla-Moledo).

gestational diabetes,^{12,13} maternal smoking,¹⁴ high maternal BMI before pregnancy and gestational weight gain^{15,16} are associated with offspring's risk of cardiovascular disease, diabetes, obesity, or their premorbid risk factors, perpetuating a cycle of adverse health outcomes.

The knowledge about the potential relationships between prenatal determinants and the main health-related physical fitness components in children and adolescents (i.e., motor fitness, cardiorespiratory fitness and muscular strength) is still very limited based on studies with a small number of fitness components, and some results are so far contradictory. In children, two studies observed that a short length of gestation was positively associated with lower cardiorespiratory fitness¹⁷ and lower muscular strength levels.^{17,18} Conversely, other studies did not find an association between physical activity during pregnancy and offspring's cardiorespiratory fitness level.^{17,19} In adolescents, some studies observed that several prenatal determinants such as maternal gestational diabetes,²⁰ maternal BMI before pregnancy,^{20,21} a short length of gestation,²⁰ or maternal smoking pregnancy²⁰ were associated with lower cardiorespiratory fitness. However, one study did not find an association between hypertensive disorders during pregnancy and cardiorespiratory fitness level.²⁰ Importantly, neither of these approaches have examined a broad range of prenatal predictors with a comprehensive physical fitness component test battery in a large sample cohort of both children and adolescents in the same study to analyze the sequential association between prenatal determinants and physical fitness outcomes.

Consequently, the main purpose of this study is to determine whether selected major gestational prenatal indicators (i.e., maternal age, maternal BMI before pregnancy, gestational weight gain, length of gestation, gestational anemia, gestational diabetes, and mother physical activity before and during pregnancy) are associated with the physical fitness outcomes (motor fitness, cardiorespiratory fitness and muscular strength) in a large sample cohort of children and adolescents. This knowledge will enable the identification of key important prenatal determinants of physical fitness in children and adolescents and can potentially contribute to the development of health promotion programs that could start even before children are born or mitigate possible adverse effects on children and adolescents.

2. Methods

2.1. Study participants

Participants were recruited from the UP&DOWN study.²² Briefly, the UP&DOWN study was a 2-year follow-up study designed to assess the impact of physical activity and sedentary behavior over time on health indicators. It also aimed to identify the psycho-environmental and genetic determinants of physical activity in a sample of Spanish children and adolescents. A total convenience sample of 2225 healthy participants aged 6–17 years participated in the UP&DOWN study, from 23 primary schools (Cádiz) and 22 secondary schools (Madrid).

In the present study, an available-case approach was used, meaning that the sample size varied across analyses depending on data availability for each specific relationship examined (i.e., maternal age, maternal BMI before pregnancy, length of gestation, gestational anemia, gestational diabetes, and physical activity before and during pregnancy and offspring's weight, height, total physical activity, and physical fitness test score). Overall, the study sample comprised 1188 children (571 girls) aged 6–11 years and 1020 adolescents (495 girls) aged 12–17 years, with an overall dropout rate of 0.76%. According to the database of the Spanish Institute of National Statistics, our sample size represents approximately 50% ($n = 1188$) of children in Cadiz and 5% ($n = 1020$) of adolescents in Madrid. Data collection was undertaken from September 2011 to June 2012.

Parents and school supervisors were informed through a letter about the study, and written informed consent was provided. The study complies with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by

the Ethics Committee of the Hospital Puerta de Hierro (Madrid, Spain), the Bioethics Committee of the National Research Council (Madrid, Spain), and the Committee for Research Involving Human Subjects at University of Cádiz (Cádiz, Spain).

2.2. Prenatal determinants

Mothers self-reported a “family questionnaire” which is a compendium of several questionnaires, validated and widely used in previous studies,^{23,24} which includes questions on several early life health determinants: *maternal age* (years), *maternal BMI before pregnancy* (kg/m^2), *gestational weight gain* (kg), *length of gestation* as a continuous (weeks) and dichotomized variable as normal length ($\geq 34 \leq 42$ weeks) or abnormal (< 34 or > 42 weeks),²⁵ *gestational anemia* (yes/no), and *gestational diabetes* (yes/no). This questionnaire also includes questions regarding *maternal physical activity before and during pregnancy* (i.e. Did the mother engage in physical activity before/during the pregnancy (no/yes)?; Which activities?; How many times per week?; How long per session?).²⁶ Thus, mothers were classified as physically active or inactive following the World Health Organization guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behavior.²⁶

2.3. Offspring

2.3.1. General characteristics

Individual-level of youth's covariates, including sex and age, were recorded. Weight and height were assessed following the protocols of the UPD&DOWN study.²²

2.3.2. Physical activity

Objectively measured physical activity was obtained by the ActiGraph accelerometer models GT1M, GT3X and GT3X+ (ActiGraph™, LLC, Pensacola, Florida). Participants wore the accelerometer on their lower back for 7 consecutive days and received instructions to remove it during sleep and water-based activities. A total of 3 days (1 weekend day) with a minimum of 10 h was the criteria for being included in the study analysis. Non-wear time was defined as a period of 60 min of zero counts and an allowance of up to two consecutive minutes in < 100 counts per minute (cpm) and with the up/down-stream 30 min consecutive of zero counts for detection of artificial movements.²⁷ Before analyses, we reintegrated data into 10-s epochs.²⁸ Wear time was computed by subtracting periods of at least 60 min of zero counts from an activity recording of at least 10 h/day. Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity was estimated using the cut-point ≥ 2000 .^{29,30} A daily weighted average (min/day) was calculated and used: $[(\text{average MVPA (min/day) on weekdays} * 5) + (\text{average MVPA (min/day) on weekend days} * 2)] / 7$.

2.3.3. Physical fitness

Physical fitness was assessed following the ALPHA health-related fitness test battery for youths which has shown to be valid and reliable in children and adolescents.³¹ All tests were performed in a single session.

Motor fitness was assessed with the 4×10 -m shuttle run test. The test was performed twice, and the fastest time was recorded in seconds. Because the motor fitness score is inversely related to high physical fitness, it was first multiplied by -1 and a higher score indicates a higher motor fitness level.

Cardiorespiratory fitness was assessed by the 20-m shuttle-run test. The test was performed once, always at the end of the session, and the last completed stage at which the subject dropped out was scored. Cardiorespiratory fitness was expressed as the total number of completed stages in the 20-m shuttle run test and treated as a continuous variable in the main analyses.

Muscular strength was assessed based on the standing long jump (lower body explosive muscular strength) and maximum handgrip strength (upper body isometric muscular strength) tests. The standing

long jump test was performed twice and the best score was recorded in centimeters. A hand dynamometer with an adjustable grip was used (TKK 5101 Grip D; Takey, Tokyo, Japan) for the handgrip strength test. The test was performed twice and the highest score in kilograms for each hand was recorded. The average score of the left and right hands was calculated. Then, scores were divided by body weight as a relative measurement of upper body muscular strength to account for differences in body size.

Additionally, a muscular fitness score was calculated as the sum of the sex- and age-standardized values of the standing long jump and handgrip strength tests divided by body weight. Moreover, a global fitness score was the sum of the sex- and age-standardized values of the 4 × 10-m shuttle run (multiplied by -1; i.e., motor fitness), 20-m shuttle run (i.e., cardiorespiratory fitness), standing long jump, and handgrip strength tests divided by body weight. For both fitness scores, a higher value is indicative of higher physical fitness levels.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Significant interactions by sex and age groups were observed in the studied associations. Consequently, analyses were performed separately for male and female children and adolescents. Descriptive statistics are presented as mean (SD), while dichotomized variables are reported as percentages. Differences between sexes were assessed using *t*-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables.

Multiple linear regression models were used to examine the association between prenatal determinants (independent variables) and children's and adolescents' physical fitness outcomes (dependent variables). Model 1 was adjusted for children's and adolescents' age; Model 2 was adjusted for the Model 1 variable plus moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA) and accelerometer wear time. Composite scores for "muscular fitness" and "global fitness" were computed for the analysis.

ANCOVA analyses were conducted to compare fitness variables across categories of maternal BMI before pregnancy, by sex and age groups. Maternal BMI was classified into three categories: normal weight (18.9–24.9 kg/m²), overweight (25.0–29.9 kg/m²), and obesity (≥30.0 kg/m²). Physical fitness outcomes, including the 4 × 10 m

(-1) (s) and 20-m shuttle run (stages) tests, muscular fitness and global fitness scores, were entered as dependent variables. Models were adjusted for children's and adolescents' age, MVPA, and accelerometer wear time. Bonferroni corrections were applied for post hoc comparisons between BMI groups. Similar ANCOVA analyses were carried out with maternal age (<35 years or ≥35 years), length of gestation (abnormal (<34 or >42 weeks) or normal (≥34 ≤42 weeks)), gestational anemia (presence or absence) and maternal physically active/physically inactive before and during pregnancy as independent variables.

As supplementary analyses, logistic regression models were performed using maternal BMI before pregnancy as the independent variable and physical fitness outcomes as the dependent variables. The normal weight group was set as the reference category (OR = 1). The 25th percentile by sex and age groups for each physical fitness variable was used as the threshold to define low and high physical fitness levels. These models were adjusted for children's and adolescents' age, MVPA, and accelerometer wear time.

All analyses were performed using SPSS software for MacOS, version 25.0 (IBM Corp). The level of statistical significance was set at *p* < 0.05.

3. Results

Table 1 presents the sample characteristics of the prenatal variables and offspring participants split by age groups and sex. The prenatal determinants are similar in both sexes, except physical activity before pregnancy. We observed a higher percentage of female children's and adolescents' mothers reporting to be physically active before pregnancy than male children's and adolescents' mothers (*p* < 0.05). In addition, male adolescents were taller and heavier than female adolescents (*p* < 0.001), and offspring males, in both age groups, reported higher moderate-to-vigorous physical activity minutes and performed better in physical fitness tests than offspring females (all *p* < 0.001).

Table 2 shows the predictive linear regression models presented adjusted by offspring variables. Model 1: adjusted by age (children and adolescents); Model 2: Model 1 + moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (min/day) and accelerometer wear time (min). Taking into account results of Model 2, in female children, higher maternal BMI before pregnancy was associated with lower levels in all physical fitness tests

Table 1
Descriptive characteristics of the study sample.

Variable	Children				Adolescents			
	n M/F	Male	Female	<i>p</i>	n M/F	Male	Female	<i>p</i>
Prenatal predictors								
Maternal age (years)	557/525	30.26 (5.47)	30.12 (5.47)	0.677	458/434	30.49 (4.69)	30.08 (4.74)	0.196
Maternal BMI before pregnancy (kg/m ²)	562/531	24.82 (4.33)	24.80 (4.31)	0.938	465/442	24.27 (3.69)	24.21 (3.59)	0.780
Gestational weight gain (kg)	543/512	12.15 (6.37)	11.90 (7.16)	0.535	444/416	10.90 (4.39)	11.02 (4.54)	0.688
Length of gestation (weeks)	541/510	38.87 (2.45)	39.06 (2.48)	0.217	430/402	38.38 (2.56)	38.26 (2.77)	0.500
Abnormal length of gestation (<34 or >42 weeks, %)	562/531	14.6	15.1	0.825	465/442	11.6	13.3	0.429
Gestational anemia (%)	544/519	25.7	25.6	0.968	455/433	13.2	17.3	0.086
Gestational diabetes (%)	546/522	8.4	9.2	0.657	456/432	7.2	6.7	0.773
Physical activity before pregnancy (%)	545/518	42.3	47.2	0.110	456/435	44.5	51.5	0.037
Physical activity during pregnancy (%)	546/518	43.8	43.2	0.844	456/436	44.3	41.1	0.328
Offspring								
<i>General characteristics</i>								
Age (years)	562/531	7.57 (1.57)	7.73 (1.56)	0.085	465/442	13.50 (1.64)	13.56 (1.62)	0.595
Height (cm)	549/525	129.30 (10.39)	129.84 (11.39)	0.416	457/439	162.77 (11.16)	157.94 (6.88)	<0.001
Weight (kg)	549/525	30.92 (9.15)	31.57 (10.21)	0.270	457/439	56.77 (13.73)	52.27 (9.71)	<0.001
Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (min/day)	451/431	82.17 (24.18)	64.71 (21.02)	<0.001	430/413	70.81 (22.88)	51.44 (14.47)	<0.001
<i>Physical fitness (test scores)</i>								
4 × 10-m test (s)	548/524	14.39 (1.70)	14.87 (1.70)	<0.001	556/433	11.78 (1.57)	12.72 (0.90)	<0.001
20-m shuttle run test (stage)	547/523	3.12 (1.70)	2.23 (1.21)	<0.001	442/416	6.61 (2.3)	4.12 (1.58)	<0.001
Standing long jump (cm)	548/525	115.77 (21.38)	107.04 (20.83)	<0.001	455/437	173.42 (32.40)	142.76 (20.96)	<0.001
Handgrip/weight (kg/kg)	549/525	0.40 (0.08)	0.38 (0.07)	<0.001	456/437	0.50 (0.10)	0.45 (0.07)	<0.001
MF score	548/525	0.00 (1.71)	-0.01 (1.68)	0.957	454/436	-0.02 (1.79)	0.08 (1.66)	0.410
Global score	547/523	0.03 (3.18)	-0.05 (3.10)	0.685	440/412	-0.07 (3.23)	0.19 (3.05)	0.231

Values expressed as mean (SD) and *p* of *t*-test for un-paired samples, or percentage and *p* of Pearson's Chi-square. Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; M/F, male and female. Statistically significant values are highlighted in bold.

Table 2
Predictive linear regression models of physical fitness test outcomes by prenatal predictors of children and adolescents.

		4 × 10 m test (−1) (s)				20-m shuttle run test (stages)				MF score				GF score			
		Males		Females		Males		Females		Males		Females		Males		Females	
		β	p	β	p	β	p	β	p	β	p	β	p	β	p	β	p
Children																	
Maternal age (years)	Model 1	−0.031	0.346	0.055	0.121	0.014	0.720	0.187	<0.001	−0.033	0.439	0.066	0.136	−0.001	0.989	0.112	0.011
	Model 2	0.051	0.132	0.035	0.353	0.049	0.230	0.169	<0.001	−0.002	0.957	0.025	0.599	0.037	0.405	0.076	0.105
Maternal BMI before pregnancy (kg/m ²)	Model 1	−0.099	0.002	−0.148	<0.001	−0.213	<0.001	−0.161	<0.001	−0.160	<0.001	−0.181	<0.001	−0.119	<0.001	−0.207	<0.001
	Model 2	−0.076	0.024	−0.115	0.002	−0.164	<0.001	−0.122	0.006	−0.140	0.002	−0.131	0.006	−0.160	<0.001	−0.156	0.001
Gestational weight gain (kg)	Model 1	−0.001	0.980	0.112	0.001	0.023	0.555	0.051	0.235	0.003	0.945	0.094	0.035	−0.002	0.958	0.110	0.014
	Model 2	0.003	0.918	0.074	0.050	0.014	0.734	0.022	0.632	−0.019	0.683	0.045	0.348	0.022	0.624	0.064	0.175
Length of gestation (weeks)	Model 1	−0.016	0.641	0.086	0.015	0.035	0.368	−0.002	0.967	0.062	0.156	−0.040	0.373	0.034	0.434	0.060	0.181
	Model 2	0.010	0.764	0.095	0.012	0.036	0.384	−0.020	0.960	0.090	0.054	−0.053	0.270	0.068	0.131	0.068	0.142
Gestational anemia (dichotomized)	Model 1	−0.074	0.026	−0.073	0.038	−0.037	0.346	−0.078	0.068	−0.053	0.224	−0.110	0.013	−0.063	0.148	−0.116	0.009
	Model 2	−0.053	0.117	−0.078	0.038	−0.055	0.180	−0.092	0.040	−0.047	0.304	−0.126	0.008	−0.062	0.162	−0.131	0.005
Gestational diabetes (dichotomized)	Model 1	0.006	0.869	−0.106	0.002	−0.052	0.183	−0.058	0.172	−0.006	0.885	−0.053	0.230	−0.003	0.946	−0.088	0.047
	Model 2	−0.028	0.409	−0.061	0.103	−0.073	0.071	−0.016	0.728	−0.027	0.553	−0.002	0.968	−0.045	0.307	−0.032	0.493
Physical activity before pregnancy (dichotomized)	Model 1	0.048	0.151	0.048	0.173	0.054	0.172	0.040	0.348	−0.009	0.834	0.059	0.182	0.033	0.444	0.057	0.202
	Model 2	0.046	0.173	0.078	0.036	0.070	0.088	0.042	0.345	−0.041	0.371	0.064	0.183	0.024	0.589	0.066	0.154
Physical activity during pregnancy (dichotomized)	Model 1	0.008	0.809	−0.011	0.758	0.051	0.194	0.023	0.588	0.016	0.705	−0.017	0.708	0.037	0.397	−0.012	0.782
	Model 2	0.012	0.716	0.032	0.391	0.057	0.161	0.070	0.121	−0.011	0.807	−0.026	0.585	0.027	0.543	0.041	0.384
Adolescents																	
Maternal age (years)	Model 1	0.079	0.042	0.193	<0.001	0.051	0.215	0.178	<0.001	0.120	0.800	0.102	0.035	0.047	0.336	0.178	<0.001
	Model 2	0.071	0.079	0.192	<0.001	0.062	0.127	0.195	<0.001	0.050	0.916	0.113	0.021	0.045	0.369	0.198	<0.001
Maternal BMI before pregnancy (kg/m ²)	Model 1	−0.144	<0.001	−0.031	0.506	−0.189	<0.001	−0.076	0.113	−0.241	<0.001	−0.109	0.024	−0.259	<0.001	−0.097	0.048
	Model 2	−0.135	<0.001	−0.043	0.367	−0.163	<0.001	−0.072	0.134	−0.236	<0.001	−0.122	0.012	−0.241	<0.001	−0.094	0.057
Gestational weight gain (kg)	Model 1	0.026	0.510	−0.021	0.660	0.031	0.460	0.024	0.636	0.019	0.701	−0.033	0.502	0.018	0.719	−0.023	0.656
	Model 2	0.022	0.584	−0.009	0.861	0.009	0.823	0.013	0.788	0.022	0.656	−0.031	0.538	0.007	0.894	0.023	0.659
Length of gestation (weeks)	Model 1	0.084	0.036	0.056	0.259	0.155	<0.001	0.104	0.040	0.120	0.014	−0.027	0.590	0.164	0.001	0.041	0.428
	Model 2	0.075	0.068	0.014	0.782	0.158	<0.001	0.075	0.141	0.102	0.044	−0.069	0.178	0.151	0.003	−0.006	0.901
Gestational anemia (dichotomized)	Model 1	−0.065	0.090	−0.023	0.621	−0.007	0.874	−0.014	0.781	−0.081	0.091	−0.007	0.893	0.078	0.106	−0.005	0.913
	Model 2	−0.058	0.149	−0.028	0.551	−0.003	0.943	−0.012	0.806	−0.064	0.196	−0.023	0.645	−0.065	0.190	−0.016	0.750
Gestational diabetes (dichotomized)	Model 1	0.015	0.702	0.005	0.915	−0.001	0.986	0.038	0.441	−0.004	0.928	0.006	0.906	0.005	0.910	0.033	0.515
	Model 2	0.021	0.604	0.029	0.548	0.002	0.955	0.064	0.193	−0.009	0.853	0.016	0.743	0.015	0.766	0.058	0.247
Physical activity before pregnancy (dichotomized)	Model 1	−0.004	0.925	0.123	0.009	0.029	0.823	0.130	0.008	−0.020	0.674	0.087	0.075	−0.012	0.799	0.133	0.008
	Model 2	−0.004	0.917	0.106	0.026	0.003	0.951	0.094	0.053	−0.029	0.558	0.072	0.145	−0.021	0.670	0.104	0.037
Physical activity during pregnancy (dichotomized)	Model 1	0.035	0.370	0.134	0.005	0.092	0.026	0.102	0.035	−0.015	0.747	0.092	0.056	0.055	0.262	0.120	0.016
	Model 2	0.018	0.649	0.132	0.006	0.080	0.050	0.108	0.035	−0.004	0.931	0.088	0.073	0.033	0.502	0.109	0.029

Analyses are presented adjusted by offspring variables. Model 1: adjusted by age (years); Model 2: Model 1 + moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (min/day) and accelerometer wear time (min). Abbreviations: MF score: muscular fitness score (standing long jump test (cm); hand grip test (kg/kg)); GF score: global fitness score (4 × 10 m test (−1) (s); 20-m shuttle run test (stage); standing long jump test (cm); hand grip test (kg/kg)). β: standardized regression coefficients. Statistically significant associations are highlighted in bold.

Note: For the 4 × 10 m shuttle run test, raw scores (time in s) were multiplied by −1 so that higher values indicate better motor fitness performance. Consequently, the direction of the β coefficients should be interpreted consistently with the other fitness outcomes: a positive β denotes that higher values in the predictor are associated with better motor fitness, and negative β denotes an association with poorer motor fitness. Statistically significant values are highlighted in bold.

Table 3
Comparison of physical fitness dimensions by maternal body mass index before pregnancy.

	Normal weight (18.9–24.9 kg/m ²)		Overweight (24.9–29.9 kg/m ²)		Obese (≥30 kg/m ²)		p vs ov	p vs ob
	n	Mean (SD)	n	Mean (SD)	n	Mean (SD)		
Male children								
4 × 10 m test (– 1) (s)	274	– 14.22 (1.70)	130	– 14.27 (1.57)	46	– 15.03 (1.40)	0.481	0.225
20-m shuttle run test (stage)	273	3.43 (1.78)	130	2.96 (1.57)	46	2.23 (1.20)	0.002	0.006
MF score	274	0.18 (1.65)	130	– 0.19 (1.75)	46	– 0.56 (1.69)	0.166	0.048
Global fitness score	273	0.47 (3.08)	130	– 0.38 (3.23)	46	– 1.13 (2.84)	0.060	0.014
Female children								
4 × 10 m test (– 1) (s)	266	– 14.65 (1.65)	113	– 14.89 (1.53)	51	– 15.70 (1.58)	1.000	0.005
20-m shuttle run test (stage)	266	2.38 (1.33)	113	2.17 (1.16)	50	1.78 (0.87)	0.663	0.124
MF score	267	0.19 (1.65)	113	0.01 (1.73)	51	– 0.74 (1.58)	1.000	0.004
Global fitness score	266	0.35 (3.09)	113	– 0.03 (3.25)	50	– 1.57 (2.70)	0.805	0.002
Male adolescents								
4 × 10 m test (– 1) (s)	285	– 11.73 (1.09)	109	– 11.74 (1.26)	34	– 12.13 (1.44)	1.000	0.002
20-m shuttle run test (stage)	277	6.78 (2.28)	104	6.50 (2.61)	34	5.94 (2.40)	0.338	0.011
MF score	283	0.18 (1.70.)	109	– 0.21 (1.87)	34	– 1.03 (1.89)	0.134	0.001
Global fitness score	275	0.32 (3.00)	104	– 0.36 (3.44)	34	– 2.22 (3.67)	0.263	<0.001
Female adolescents								
4 × 10 m test (– 1) (s)	268	– 12.71 (0.93)	106	– 12.71 (0.77)	34	– 12.73 (0.99)	1.000	1.000
20-m shuttle run test (stage)	256	4.11 (1.64)	103	4.20 (1.39)	32	3.62 (1.59)	1.000	0.371
MF score	270	0.12 (1.70)	107	0.58 (1.50)	34	0.47 (1.58)	1.000	0.102
Global fitness score	254	0.26 (3.12)	102	0.15 (2.72)	32	– 0.55 (3.31)	1.000	0.430

Values are expressed as mean (standard deviation) and p of ANCOVA with Bonferroni's correction for differences between groups compared to normal weight. Analyses were adjusted by age (years), moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (min/day) of children and adolescents and accelerometer wear time (min).

Abbreviations: SD: standard deviation; MF score: muscular fitness score (standing long jump test (cm); hand grip test (kg/kg)); GF score: global fitness score (4 × 10 m test (– 1) (s); 20-m shuttle run test (stage); standing long jump test (cm); hand grip test (kg/kg)). Statistically significant values are highlighted in bold.

(i.e., motor fitness, cardiorespiratory fitness, muscular fitness score and global fitness score) ($\beta = -0.115; -0.122; -0.131; -0.156$, all $p < 0.05$, respectively). Moreover, having gestational anemia was associated with lower levels in all physical fitness tests (i.e., motor fitness, cardiorespiratory fitness, muscular fitness score and global fitness score) ($\beta = -0.078; -0.092; -0.126; -0.131$, all $p < 0.05$, respectively). Lower maternal gestational weight gain, normal length

of gestation ($\geq 34 \leq 42$ weeks) and to be physically active before pregnancy were associated with higher motor fitness levels ($\beta = 0.074; 0.095; 0.078$, all $p < 0.05$, respectively), and a higher maternal age (≥ 35 years) was associated with a higher cardiorespiratory fitness level ($\beta = 0.169, p < 0.001$).

In female adolescents, higher maternal BMI before pregnancy was associated with lower muscular fitness ($\beta = -0.122, p = 0.012$) and

Table 4
Comparison of physical fitness dimensions by length of gestation (abnormal vs normal) and presence or not of maternal physical activity before and during pregnancy in female adolescents.

	Length of gestation				p (Model 1)	p (Model 2)
	Abnormal (<34 or >42 weeks)		Normal (≥34 ≤ 42 weeks)			
	n	Mean (SD)	n	Mean (SD)		
Female adolescents						
4 × 10 m (– 1) (s)	58	– 12.70 (0.89)	375	– 12.85 (0.88)	0.623	0.019
20-m shuttle run test (stage)	57	4.13 (1.63)	359	3.90 (1.27)	0.571	0.303
MF score	58	0.48 (1.65)	378	0.11 (1.68)	0.668	0.013
Global fitness score	57	0.19 (3.07)	355	– 0.00 (2.81)	0.935	0.023
Maternal physical activity before pregnancy						
					p (Model 1)	p (Model 2)
Physically inactive		Physically active				
n	Mean (SD)	n	Mean (SD)			
Female adolescents						
4 × 10 m (– 1) (s)	204	– 12.80 (0.86)	223	– 12.64 (0.91)	0.009	0.026
20-m shuttle run test (stage)	195	3.95 (1.60)	215	4.24 (1.57)	0.008	0.053
MF score	207	– 0.07 (1.58)	223	0.17 (1.71)	0.075	0.145
Global fitness score	191	– 0.20 (2.98)	215	0.50 (3.06)	0.008	0.037
Maternal physical activity during pregnancy						
					p (Model 1)	p (Model 2)
Physically inactive		Physically active				
n	Mean (SD)	n	Mean (SD)			
Female adolescents						
4 × 10 m (– 1) (s)	253	– 12.80 (0.89)	175	– 12.60 (0.88)	0.005	<0.001
20-m shuttle run test (stage)	242	3.99 (1.57)	169	4.25 (1.60)	0.035	0.035
MF score	255	– 0.62 (1.68)	176	0.20 (1.60)	0.056	0.073
Global fitness score	239	– 0.11 (3.08)	168	0.54 (2.95)	0.016	0.029

Values are expressed as mean (standard deviation) and p of ANCOVA adjusted by age (Model 1) and by age and moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (min/day) of children and adolescents and accelerometer wear time (min) (Model 2). Abbreviations: SD: standard deviation; MF score: muscular fitness score (standing long jump test (cm); handgrip test (kg/kg)); GF score: global fitness score (4 × 10 m test (– 1) (s); 20-m shuttle run test (stage); standing long jump test (cm); hand grip test (kg/kg)). Statistically significant values are highlighted in bold.

lower global fitness scores (border line; $\beta = -0.094$, $p = 0.057$). Higher maternal age (≥ 35 years) was associated with higher scores of all physical fitness tests ($\beta = 0.192$; 0.195 ; 0.113 ; 0.198 , all $p < 0.05$, respectively). Likewise, to be physically active before and during pregnancy was associated with higher motor fitness ($\beta = 0.106$; 0.132 , all $p < 0.05$, respectively), higher cardiorespiratory fitness (borderline; $\beta = 0.094$; 0.108 , all $p < 0.05$, respectively) and higher global fitness scores ($\beta = 0.104$; 0.109 , all $p < 0.05$, respectively).

In male children and adolescents, higher maternal BMI before pregnancy was associated with lower motor fitness ($\beta = -0.076$; -0.135 , all $p < 0.05$, respectively), cardiorespiratory fitness ($\beta = -0.164$; -0.163 , all $p < 0.01$, respectively), muscular fitness score ($\beta = -0.140$; -0.236 , all $p < 0.001$, respectively) and global fitness levels ($\beta = -0.160$; -0.241 , all $p < 0.001$, respectively).

Lastly, in male adolescents, a normal length of gestation ($\geq 34 \leq 42$ weeks) was associated with higher cardiorespiratory fitness ($\beta = 0.158$, $p < 0.001$), muscular fitness score ($\beta = 0.102$, $p = 0.044$) and higher global fitness levels ($\beta = 0.151$, $p = 0.003$), and to be physically active during pregnancy was associated with a higher cardiorespiratory fitness level (borderline, $\beta = 0.080$, $p = 0.050$).

Table 3 remarks that all offspring with obese mothers scored lower in all physical fitness tests (all $p < 0.05$) than those counterparts with normal weight mothers, with the following exceptions: male children in motor fitness, female children in cardiorespiratory fitness, and female adolescents in all fitness test scores. In addition (Table S1), female children and male adolescents with obese mothers showed lower odds of having high scores in motor fitness, cardiorespiratory fitness, muscular fitness and global fitness compared to those of normal weight mothers (all $p < 0.05$). Male children with obese mothers showed lower odds of having higher scores in muscular fitness and global fitness compared to those of normal weight mothers (all $p < 0.05$). Moreover, male and female children with overweight mothers showed lower odds of having high scores in muscular fitness and global fitness compared to those of normal weight mothers (all $p < 0.05$).

Furthermore (Table 4), female adolescents whose mothers reported to have an abnormal length of gestation (< 34 or > 42 weeks) and to be physically inactive before and during pregnancy scored lower in all physical fitness tests (all $p < 0.05$) than those counterparts whose mothers reported to have a normal length of gestation ($\geq 34 \leq 42$ weeks) and to perform physical activity before and during pregnancy, except cardiorespiratory fitness in an abnormal length of gestation, and muscular fitness score in being physically inactive before and during pregnancy. We only included offspring female adolescents' data in this table because in the other groups we did not find significant results (see Table S2).

4. Discussion

Our findings indicate that the strongest prenatal determinant of offspring physical fitness was **maternal BMI before pregnancy**, with higher maternal BMI being associated with lower physical fitness levels in offspring, regardless of age and sex. This was followed by **maternal physical activity during and before pregnancy**, where offspring of mothers who were physically active before and during pregnancy exhibited higher physical fitness levels, specifically in female adolescents. Additionally, the **length of gestation** was positively associated with physical fitness in male adolescents. Moreover, the **absence of gestational anemia** was related to higher physical fitness levels in female children. Notably, offspring of mothers with a normal weight before pregnancy exhibited significantly higher physical fitness levels than those born of mothers with obesity, except in female adolescents. However, among female adolescents, those whose mothers reported to have a normal length of gestation ($\geq 34 \leq 42$) and/or were physically active before and during pregnancy displayed higher overall physical fitness levels.

During the past 2 decades, the prevalence of obesity has increased rapidly across all age groups, including the percentage of overweight

or obese women of reproductive age.³² In our study, we observed that higher maternal BMI before pregnancy was the major prenatal determinant prognosticating lower scores of all physical fitness tests in offspring, regardless of age and sex. Thus, all offspring with obese mothers scored lower in all physical fitness tests (all $p < 0.05$) than those counterparts with normal weight mothers. The pathway explaining our results might be in part because of cord blood leptin being higher in obese mothers and high levels of leptin are associated with lower cardiorespiratory fitness in adults which might affect as well fetal muscle growth and/or other parameters.³³ In line with our study, previous research suggests that higher maternal BMI before pregnancy (overweight/obesity) was associated with reduced cardiorespiratory fitness level in children and adolescents, respectively.^{20,21} In contrast, Mintjens et al.²¹ conducted a study only with children and they did not observe an association of higher maternal BMI before pregnancy (overweight/obesity) with upper body muscular strength. Differences between our results and Mintjens et al.'s²¹ regarding muscular strength might be due to the following: 1) the limited sample size (194) they used, 2) the age of the children included in the trial (8 years old) in contrast with our study which includes a wide range (6–11 years old), and 3) this study only measured upper body muscular strength but in our study we included a muscular fitness score (upper body isometric muscular strength and lower body explosive muscular strength).

The second more predictive prenatal determinant was maternal physical activity before and during pregnancy. Research continues to confirm that exercise during pregnancy contributes to healthier outcomes for both the mother and the fetus^{34,35} and is currently recommended in all low risk pregnancies.³⁴ However, studies looking at the relationships between women who are physical inactive or active during pregnancy and offspring's physical fitness are limited. In our study, offspring of mothers who were physically active before and during pregnancy exhibited higher physical fitness levels, specifically in female adolescents. As far as we know, there is only one study conducted with a very small sample (12 women and their children (8–10 years old)) who did not observe any association between physical activity during pregnancy and cardiorespiratory fitness, which is in line with our study.¹⁹

Potential pathways explaining the relation between mothers' physical activity and offspring's physical fitness have been proposed. Previous research found that higher levels of light or moderate physical activity during pregnancy were associated with greater umbilical arterial oxygen saturation and higher levels of venous cord blood pH, crucial for appropriate nutrient and gas exchange with the fetus,³⁶ which could provide a rationale of the association between active mothers and offspring's cardiorespiratory fitness. On the other way, postnatal muscle growth is mainly driven by increases in the size of muscle fibers rather than increases in fiber number, which is largely established at birth.³⁷ Thus, the metabolic status of the mother could affect offspring skeletal muscle development and muscular strength as well.³⁸ However, the mechanism that might explain why the maternal level of physical activity is associated with physical fitness in adolescents, particularly in females is still unclear. In our study we observed a higher percentage of female adolescents' mothers reporting to be physically active before pregnancy than male adolescents' mothers. Females are more likely to be influenced by their mothers' physical activity behaviors and encouragement compared to males,³⁹ which could explain our results. The lack of previous studies prevents comparison with the results of the present study. Additional research is needed to contrast our findings.

In addition, we observed that a normal length of gestation ($\geq 34 \leq 42$ weeks) was positively associated with higher overall physical fitness levels except cardiorespiratory fitness in female adolescents, whereas several studies observed that a short length of gestation (< 34 weeks) was positively associated with lower cardiorespiratory fitness in children¹⁷ and adolescents,²⁰ and lower motor fitness and lower body explosive muscular strength levels than those born full

term in children and adolescents.¹⁸ The mechanism explaining this influence might be due to the association between the short length of gestation and the increased risk of neurodevelopment impairments,^{25,40} which would limit scores in all fitness tests based on muscular strength-related fitness due to required neuromotor control, compared to offspring born in a normal range of length of gestation.

Lastly, the absence of gestational anemia was related to higher levels in all physical fitness tests in female children. Different pathways could be proposed to explain this relation. It might be noted that offspring whose mothers reported to have suffered gestational anemia could be affected by iron deficiency⁴¹ and functional iron deficiency, plus limited oxygen supply in anemic mothers, might affect offspring skeletal muscle development, muscular strength³⁸ and cardiorespiratory fitness performance.⁴² To our knowledge, this is the first research investigating the association of gestational anemia with a multicomponent fitness assessment in children and adolescents, which prevents the possibility of comparing present results with other similar studies.

The current study presents several limitations. Firstly, the sample size and distribution were not fully representative of the Spanish youth; therefore, caution should be taken with the generalizability of the results. However, it is a very large sample cohort. Another limitation refers to the fact that prenatal determinants were self-reported but we used validated and widely used questions in previous studies.^{23,24} An additional limitation may be the long time period between prenatal exposure and maternal retrospective self-report, which could be associated with some recall bias.

The strengths of our study include that, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study investigating the association of a wide range of prenatal determinants including a comprehensive list of all physical fitness components (motor fitness, cardiorespiratory fitness, muscular fitness score) and global fitness score in a large cohort with a full range of age (6–17 years). In addition, objectively and validated measurements of offspring's components of physical fitness and physical activity were done.

5. Conclusion

This study found that higher maternal BMI before pregnancy, physical inactivity before and during pregnancy, abnormal gestational length, and gestational anemia were associated with lower offspring physical fitness, particularly among female adolescents. While these results suggest that maternal health and behaviors during pregnancy may influence offspring fitness, the observational design does not allow for causal inference. Future intervention studies are warranted to clarify these relationships and confirm whether improving maternal health before and during pregnancy can positively affect children's physical fitness. Our findings highlight the relevance of maternal health as a potential early determinant of offspring physical fitness and provide a foundation for future research in this field.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Carmen Padilla-Moledo: Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Alejandro Pérez-Bey:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Sandra Sánchez-Parente:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Rocio Izquierdo-Gómez:** Writing – review & editing. **Oscar L. Veiga:** Investigation, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Jose Castro-Piñero:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Project administration, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Patient consent

Parental/guardian and school supervisors consent obtained.

Confirmation of ethical compliance

The study complies with the Declaration of Helsinki and protocols were approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital Puerta de Hierro (Madrid, Spain), the Bioethics Committee of the National Research Council (Madrid, Spain), and the Committee for Research Involving Human Subjects at University of Cádiz.

Funding information

This work was supported by grant DEP 2010-21662-C04-00 (DEP 2010-21662-C04-01; DEP 2010-21662-C04-02; DEP 2010-21662-C04-03; DEP 2010-21662-C04-04) from the National Plan for Research: Development and Innovation (R&D&I) MICINN and by grant FPU15/05337 from the Spanish Ministry of Education. CPM thanks the Promotion and Encouragement Research Activity Programme of the University of Cádiz (Spain) for their support.

Declaration of interest statement

None of the authors had any conflict of interest. No benefits in any form have been received or will be received from a commercial party related directly or indirectly to the subject of this article.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by grant DEP 2010-21662-C04-00 (DEP 2010-21662-C04-01; DEP 2010-21662-C04-02; DEP 2010-21662-C04-03; DEP 2010-21662-C04-04) from the National Plan for Research: Development and Innovation (R&D&I) MICINN and by grant FPU15/05337 from the Spanish Ministry of Education. CPM thanks the Promotion and Encouragement Research Activity Programme of the University of Cádiz (Spain) for their support. We thank all the members involved in the field work; as well as children and adolescents, parents, headmasters and teachers of the participating schools.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2026.01.011>.

References

- Heindel JJ, Vandenberg LN. Developmental origins of health and disease: a paradigm for understanding disease cause and prevention. *Curr Opin Pediatr* 2015;27:248–253. doi:10.1097/mop.0000000000000191.
- Perez-Sousa MA, Olivares PR, Escobar-Alvarez JA et al. Fitness as mediator between weight status and dimensions of health-related quality of life. *Health Qual Life Outcomes* 2018;16:155. doi:10.1186/s12955-018-0981-0.
- Perez-Sousa MA, Olivares PR, Garcia-Hermoso A et al. Fitness as a mediator of the enhancement of quality of life after a 6-months exercise program. *Res Q Exerc Sport* 2020;91:24–33. doi:10.1080/02701367.2019.1645939.
- Ortega FB, Ruiz JR, Castillo MJ et al. Physical fitness in childhood and adolescence: a powerful marker of health. *Int J Obes (Lond)* 2008;32:1–11. doi:10.1038/sj.ijo.0803774.[0803774 pii].
- Castro-Piñero J, Perez-Bey A, Segura-Jimenez V et al. Cardiorespiratory fitness cutoff points for early detection of present and future cardiovascular risk in children: a 2-year follow-up study. *Mayo Clin Proc* 2017;92:1753–1762. doi:10.1016/j.mayocp.2017.09.003.
- Castro-Piñero J, Perez-Bey A, Cuenca-García M et al. Muscle fitness cut points for early assessment of cardiovascular risk in children and adolescents. *J Pediatr* 2019;206:134–141.e3. doi:10.1016/j.jpeds.2018.10.026.
- Demchenko I, Prince SA, Merucci K et al. Cardiorespiratory fitness and health in children and adolescents: an overview of systematic reviews with meta-analyses representing over 125 000 observations covering 33 health-related outcomes. *Br J Sports Med* 2025. doi:10.1136/bjsports-2024-109184.
- García-Hermoso A, Ramírez-Campillo R, Izquierdo M. Is muscular fitness associated with future health benefits in children and adolescents? A systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *Sports Med* 2019. doi:10.1007/s40279-019-01098-6.
- Cattuzzo MT, Dos Santos Henrique R, Ré AH et al. Motor competence and health related physical fitness in youth: a systematic review. *J Sci Med Sport* 2016;19:123–129. doi:10.1016/j.jsams.2014.12.004.

10. Andersen JR, Natvig GK, Aadland E et al. Associations between health-related quality of life, cardiorespiratory fitness, muscle strength, physical activity and waist circumference in 10-year-old children: the ask study. *Qual Life Res* 2017;26:3421–3428. doi:10.1007/s11136-017-1634-1.
11. Chiang HL, Chuang YF, Chen YA et al. Physical fitness and risk of mental disorders in children and adolescents. *JAMA Pediatr* 2024;178:595–607. doi:10.1001/jamapediatrics.2024.0806.
12. Gu Y, Lu J, Li W et al. Joint associations of maternal gestational diabetes and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy with overweight in offspring. *Front Endocrinol* 2019;10:645. doi:10.3389/fendo.2019.00645.
13. Manuella J, Verdejo-Román J, Torres Espinola F et al. Influence of gestational diabetes and pregestational maternal bmi on the brain of six-year-old offspring. *Pediatr Neurol* 2022;133:55–62. doi:10.1016/j.pediatrneurol.2022.05.005.
14. Philips EM, Santos S, Trasande L et al. Changes in parental smoking during pregnancy and risks of adverse birth outcomes and childhood overweight in europe and north america: an individual participant data meta-analysis of 229,000 singleton births. *PLoS Med* 2020;17:e1003182. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.1003182.
15. Bhattacharya S, McNeill G, Raja EA et al. Maternal gestational weight gain and offspring's risk of cardiovascular disease and mortality. *Heart (Br Card Soc)* 2016;102:1456–1463. doi:10.1136/heartjnl-2015-308709.
16. Larque E, Labayen I, Flodmark CE et al. From conception to infancy — early risk factors for childhood obesity. *Nat Rev Endocrinol* 2019;15:456–478. doi:10.1038/s41574-019-0219-1.
17. Martínez-Zamora MD, Valenzuela PL, Esteban Díez I et al. Influence of preterm birth on physical fitness in early childhood. *Eur J Sport Sci* 2023;23:2129–2138. doi:10.1080/17461391.2023.2207082.
18. Robič Pikel T, Starc G, Strel J et al. Impact of prematurity on exercise capacity and agility of children and youth aged 8 to 18. *Early Hum Dev* 2017;110:39–45. doi:10.1016/j.earlhumdev.2017.04.015.
19. Pivarnik JM, Mudd LM, White EE et al. Physical activity during pregnancy and offspring characteristics at 8–10 years. *J Sports Med Phys Fitness* 2014;54:672–679.
20. Tikanmaki M, Tammelin T, Vaarasma M et al. Prenatal determinants of physical activity and cardiorespiratory fitness in adolescence — northern finland birth cohort 1986 study. *BMC Public Health* 2017;17:346. doi:10.1186/s12889-017-4237-4.
21. Mintjens S, Gemke R, van Poppel MNM et al. Maternal prepregnancy overweight and obesity are associated with reduced physical fitness but do not affect physical activity in childhood: the Amsterdam born children and their development study. *Child Obes (Print)* 2019;15:31–39. doi:10.1089/chi.2018.0171.
22. Castro-Pinero J, Carbonell-Baeza A, Martínez-Gomez D et al. Follow-up in healthy schoolchildren and in adolescents with down syndrome: psycho-environmental and genetic determinants of physical activity and its impact on fitness, cardiovascular diseases, inflammatory biomarkers and mental health; the UP&DOWN study. *BMC Public Health* 2014;14:400. doi:10.1186/1471-2458-14-400.
23. Hallal PC, Wells JC, Reichert FF et al. Early determinants of physical activity in adolescence: prospective birth cohort study. *Bmj* 2006;332:1002–1007. doi:10.1136/bmj.38776.434560.7C.
24. Mattocks C, Deere K, Leary S et al. Early life determinants of physical activity in 11 to 12 year olds: cohort study. *Br J Sports Med* 2008;42:721–724.
25. Sipola-Leppanen M, Vaarasma M, Tikanmaki M et al. Cardiovascular risk factors in adolescents born preterm. *Pediatrics* 2014;134:e1072–e1081. doi:10.1542/peds.2013-4186.
26. Bull FC, Al-Ansari SS, Biddle S et al. World health organization 2020 guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour. *Br J Sports Med* 2020;54:1451–1462. doi:10.1136/bjsports-2020-102955.
27. Choi L, Liu Z, Matthews CE et al. Validation of accelerometer wear and nonwear time classification algorithm. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 2011;43:357–364. doi:10.1249/MSS.0b013e3181ed61a3.
28. Cain KL, Sallis JF, Conway TL et al. Using accelerometers in youth physical activity studies: a review of methods. *J Phys Act Health* 2013;10:437–450. doi:10.1123/jpah.10.3.437.
29. Martínez-Gomez D, Ruiz JR, Ortega FB et al. Recommended levels of physical activity to avoid an excess of body fat in european adolescents: the HELENA Study. *Am J Prev Med* 2010;39:203–211. doi:10.1016/j.amepre.2010.05.003.
30. Ruiz JR, Ortega FB, Martínez-Gómez D et al. Objectively measured physical activity and sedentary time in european adolescents: the HELENA Study. *Am J Epidemiol* 2011;174:173–184. doi:10.1093/aje/kwr068.
31. Ruiz JR, Castro-Pinero J, Espana-Romero V et al. Field-based fitness assessment in young people: the ALPHA health-related fitness test battery for children and adolescents. *Br J Sports Med* 2011;45:518–524. doi:10.1136/bjsm.2010.075341.
32. WHO (World Health Organization). Obesity and overweight. WHO fact sheet no. 311. Available from: <http://www.Who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs311/en/> 2014.
33. Ferrara A. Increasing prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus: a public health perspective. *Diabetes Care* 2007;30(Suppl 2):S141–S146. doi:10.2337/dc07-s206.
34. ACOG Committee opinion no. 650: physical activity and exercise during pregnancy and the postpartum period. *Obstet Gynecol* 2015;126:e135–e142. doi:10.1097/aog.0000000000001214.
35. Newton ER, May L. Adaptation of maternal-fetal physiology to exercise in pregnancy: the basis of guidelines for physical activity in pregnancy. *Clin Med Insights Womens Health* 2017;10:1179562x17693224. doi:10.1177/1179562x17693224.
36. Baena-García L, Ocon-Hernandez O, Acosta-Manzano P et al. Association of sedentary time and physical activity during pregnancy with maternal and neonatal birth outcomes. The GESTAFIT Project. *Scand J Med Sci Sports* 2019;29:407–414. doi:10.1111/sms.13337.
37. Mikovic J, Lamson S. The effect of maternal metabolic status on offspring health: a role for skeletal muscle? *J Physiol* 2018;596:5079–5080. doi:10.1113/jp276929.
38. Bouchard C, Leon AS, Rao DC et al. The heritage family study. Aims, design, and measurement protocol. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 1995;27:721–729.
39. Yoon H, Lee S, Ju Y et al. The relationship between physical activity level of parents and that of their adolescent children. *J Phys Act Health* 2018;15(8):613–619. doi:10.1123/jpah.2017-0123.
40. Sa de Almeida J, Meskaldji DE, Loukas S et al. Preterm birth leads to impaired rich-club organization and fronto-paralimbic/limbic structural connectivity in newborns. *NeuroImage* 2021;225:117440. doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2020.117440.
41. Siddappa AM, Rao R, Long JD et al. The assessment of newborn iron stores at birth: a review of the literature and standards for ferritin concentrations. *Neonatology* 2007;92:73–82. doi:10.1159/000100805.
42. Mitchell T, McKinnon E, Ayonrinde O et al. Decreased physical working capacity in adolescents with nonalcoholic fatty liver disease associates with reduced iron availability. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2020;18:1584–1591. doi:10.1016/j.cgh.2019.10.017.